

CHAPTER-III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present chapter discusses the research design adopted in this study covering the following aspects. Figure 3.1 charts out the stepwise framework adopted to conduct this research

Figure 3.1: Organization of Research

3.1 Statement of Problem

The detailed review of literature has revealed that Tourism has been a strongly established discipline in certain developed countries that are performing exceptionally well in global tourism. Hence, literature that has addressed tourism education is primarily concentrated in developed countries. In a country like India tourism studies are still at a nascent stage as the discipline has been aggressively incorporated in

academics only in the last 3 decades. Besides there are limited studies that provide an overview of institutions that offer tourism education and the kinds of programs offered. Almost negligible research is available regarding the 'status and quality' of tourism education in India. Keeping this in view, the following topic is identified for the present research:

“Tourism Education in India: Perception of Academicians and Industry Professionals”

3.2 Need of the Study

The literature review highlights that tourism research has not delved much into investigating the quality of tourism education being imparted in countries, its relevance for the actual industry and its applicability in national tourism planning and policy making.

With respect to India, it is noted that though tourism education started in late 1980s at higher educational institutions, till date no national uniform curriculum has been adopted by institutions imparting tourism education. Further, there is an apparent mismatch between the education and skills provided through tourism programs at institutions and those desired by the industry. Besides at government level there is no initiative to knit together the input of tourism professionals into government tourism planning and policy making.

There is a disconnect between tourism education and tourism implementation bodies. While the academics are of the view that they are producing able professionals the industry do not have a same view.

Though studies have been carried out in India on nature of tourism education in the country and its importance, research is strikingly lacking in 'assessing the perception of stakeholders with regards to tourism education'. In light of this research gap, this study aims at identifying the similarities and differences in perception of tourism education in India in the eyes of tourism academicians as compared to tourism industry professionals. It is intended that this study can be of great significance to understand and highlight the gap between tourism academics and industry required skills. A fair assessment of the nature of quality of tourism education can help to mold and reframe tourism education in a manner that its utility can be realized in the industry.

3.3 Scope of Study

In the present times every country is strengthening its tourism industry to attract a larger share of global tourists. Tourism education and professionalism becomes very important to enhance the competitiveness of any tourism destination. Considering tourism as significant aspect of the economy countries worldwide are either introducing tourism education or strengthening the existing education. Continuous new orientations and reskilling are need of the hour for moving tourism sector. Besides the contribution that tourism professionals can make to the growth of the industry cannot be undermined. Therefore, the study can be highly beneficial covering the areas of academics, industry and national tourism bodies.

3.4 Objectives of Study

In order to provide answers to the status of tourism education in India, its quality and drawbacks, the following objectives have been formulated for the present study.

Perception of tourism academicians

1. To identify the public institutions in the country that are providing tourism education.
2. To identify the nature of tourism programs and its content being offered
3. To find out the process of tourism course curriculum development
4. To examine the profile of students opting for tourism education
5. To assess the nature of knowledge and skill development through the programs being offered

Perception of tourism industry professionals

1. To identify company information of the enterprise and information of the professionals
2. To investigate the nature of services being offered by the travel company
3. To examine the profile of employees working in the company
4. To understand the knowledge and skills of fresh employees
5. To identify the opinion of tourism professionals regarding the quality of tourism education being imparted to the tourism graduates.

3.5 Research Questions

Based on the Research Objectives, the study attempts to answer the following research questions

- What is the nature of institutions imparting tourism education and the nature of travel company employing tourism graduates?
- What kind of tourism programs are being offered by the institutions and how is the program curriculum designed?
- In what areas and through what knowledge component do the programs aim at molding tourism professionals?
- What is the nature and qualification of the graduates/employees joining the travel enterprises?
- What is the perception of industry professionals and academicians regarding quality of education being provided to tourism graduates and what are the areas that need attention for improvement?

3.6 Design and Framework

3.6.1 Sampling Strategy

Clustered sampling was used for the study. Two clusters were decided upon i.e. 1. Tourism Academicians and, 2. Travel Industry Professionals.

Only the public universities offering tourism education were chosen for the study. All tourism academicians working in these universities (about 500) were contacted through their available emails to fill up the questionnaire sent online by the researcher.

With regard to procuring data from Travel Industry Professionals only Travel companies that are 'active members' of Indian Association of Tour Operator (IATO) were contacted. About 700 travel companies were contacted to procure data. An online questionnaire was sent to procure data in a year period from December 2018 to December 2019.

By the end of a one year period i.e. in December 2019, only 129 filled questionnaires were received from academicians. Hence on a first response basis the cut off for taking filled in questionnaires from Travel Professionals was marked at an equal number of first received 129 filled in questionnaires from Travel Professionals.

An equal number of 129 respondents from both clusters was finally taken for comparative purpose.

3.6.2 Sample size

Number of respondents (Academicians)	- 129
Number of respondents (Tourism Professionals)	- 129
Total Respondents	- 258

3.7 Data Sources

For the purpose of fulfillment of objectives, both secondary and primary data have been used. While literature review has been conducted through secondary resources to identify the research problem, primary study with the use of questionnaire has been administered for collecting data to arrive at results for the objectives identified for the study.

3.7.1 Secondary Data

Secondary data was extensively consulted for literature review and for studying the tourism education history, innovations, industry demand, academic approach, future of tourism education. Secondary sources were accessed through libraries in the form of books, journals and reports on subjects of tourism education curriculum, tourism studies, future of tourism education, and sociology of tourism. Journals like, Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism, Journal of Travel Research, Journal of Tourism Studies, and International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management provided valuable insight into research on tourism education, tourism industry professionals, future of tourism education, Indian tourism education and Indian tourism industry.

Secondary data from the World Economic Forum, World Bank, was also consulted to see the trend of contribution of Indian tourism industry in employment and GDP. Web access was sought to consult reports on skill development, government initiatives to promote tourism and its major goals.

3.7.2 Primary Data

Primary data was collected through the aid of a self-designed Questionnaire. Initially a pilot study was conducted, taking 40 academicians/professionals randomly in order to test the adaptability and validity of the questionnaire. Based on the

preliminary results, necessary changes were incorporated in the final questionnaire drawn out to undertake the final study.

3.8 Questionnaire Design

Two set of questionnaire were prepared to obtain desired information in a comprehensive manner. The questionnaire was divided into various sections to obtain information on the following aspects:

3.8.1 Questionnaire for tourism academicians

Section A: Aimed at studying the Institutional as well as ‘academician’s profile’:

This section covers name of the organisation, department affiliation, specialization offered and area of specialization and years of teaching as a tourism academicians.

Section B: Aimed at studying the ‘program information’:

This section comprises of nature of tourism courses offered, General course component included in tourism program (s) offered and tourism specific component included in tourism program (s) offered.

Section C: Aimed at studying the course framework in department/institute:

This section includes course curriculum development and infrastructure facilities available for students in department/institute.

Section D: Aimed at studying the student profile in department/institute:

This section has questions pertaining to the educational background, schooling/graduation background, origin of students and dropout rate of students.

Section E: Aimed at rating of student skill (s) developed after completion of tourism program:

This section comprises the rating of 12 different skills on five point Likert scale.

Section F: Aimed at rating of academicians’ opinion about tourism education and its improvement in the country:

Section F comprises several statements on opinion of academicians regarding requisite improvement in frequent syllabus update, industry interaction, job training, research, foreign language, tourism software training, digital skills, library resources, academia-industry networking, and student exchange program for quality education in department/institute. There are questions on rating of tourism education in country, satisfaction with tourism education

imparted in department, type of networking beneficial for tourism education, opinion on relevance of tourism education for international peace, National image building, sustainable development, economic development and environment conservation. It also has questions on incorporation of Indian Tourism Services (ITS) for tourism graduates and specified opinion of academicians on tourism education and its improvement in India.

3.8.2 Questionnaire for tourism professionals.

Section A: Aimed at studying the company as well as professional's profile: This section covers name of the organisation, designation, department name (respondent working for), business typology, operation typology, specialization offered & area of specialization, no. of employees in company and no. of years serving in tourism industry.

Section B: Aimed at studying services offered by company of respondent: In this section comprises of nature of services offered by company, specific department in company, must require skills from employees at the time of hiring, role of company in tourism education, rating of statements on tourism specific knowledge required in company and participation in tourism education curriculum development.

Section C: Aimed at analysing the employees' educational back ground: This section includes educational background of employees and state of origin in the concerned organisation of respondent.

Section D: Aimed at studying employee (tourism graduate) capability at the time of hiring: This section have questions pertaining to rating of 12 different skills at the time of hiring the tourism graduates.

Section E: Aimed at rating of professionals' opinion about tourism education and its improvement in the country: Section F comprises of rating of tourism education being provided in the country, opinion of tourism professionals regarding requisite improvement in frequent syllabus update, industry interaction, job training, research, foreign language, tourism software training, digital skills, library resources, academia-industry networking, and student exchange program for quality education in department/institute. There are questions on rating of produced tourism professionals in country, type of networking beneficial for tourism education, opinion on relevance of tourism education for international peace, national image building, sustainable

development, economic development and environment conservation. It also have questions on incorporation of Indian Tourism Services (ITS) for tourism graduates and specified opinion of tourism professionals on tourism education and its improvement in India.

3.9 Methodology

The following procedures were used for analysis and representation of data:

Statistical and Graphical methods.

1. Statistical Methods

SPSS 20 was used for analysis of data.

The following methods were used

- (a) **Descriptive Tests: Frequencies, Percentages:** Descriptive tests are used to describe the perception/characteristics of the sample or population in totality. They limit generalization to the particular group of individuals observed or studied. In the present research Frequencies, Percentages, Mean, Standard Deviation, Crosstab have been used to analyse data.

(b) **Standard**

Deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}$$

σ (sigma)

μ (mu), represents mean of all values,

N, represents total number of values,

x_i represents individual x values

- (c) **Crosstabs:** A crosstab table is a special type of frequency distribution table, where two or more variables are shown simultaneously. It was used to show the proportion of cases in subgroups. It provides frequency distribution with count.

2. Graphical Methods

In the present study the findings are presented with help of the tables, graphs, charts and word cloud images, where needed.

3.10 Delimitation of the Study

For the research only ‘public sector universities’ in higher education were considered and only IATO active travel companies were taken for responses.

3.11 Limitation

Due to time and monetary constraints and the widely dispersed geographical location of public universities offering tourism education in the country and of IATO active travel companies, it was not possible for the researcher to collect all data in person. Hence only online questionnaires were used that might have had an element of incomprehensibility in terms of respondent providing data. Hence data procured through electronic questionnaire had to be relied upon.

The sample size had to be restricted to 258 respondents (129 of each cluster) as due to time limitation, the data procurement was limited to one year period.